

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18670917

Impact Of Online Counselling on Stress-Management and Self-Efficacy of Undergraduate Students

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigated the Impact of Online Counselling on Stress-Management and Self-Efficacy of Undergraduate Students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population comprised 25,843 undergraduates across eight faculties, from which a sample of 394 students was drawn using Glenn's (1994) formula for sample size determination and a multi-stage sampling procedure was utilized. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Online Counselling and Psycho-Academic Adjustment Scale (OCPAS), which had a reliability coefficient of 0.96. The instrument contained 30 items rated on a four-point Likert scale. The instrument. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while the Chi-square (χ^2) goodness-of-fit test was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that online counselling has a significant impact on stress management and self-efficacy of undergraduates. The study concluded that online counselling enhances students' motivation, emotional stability, time management, and overall academic engagement, thereby improving their Stress Management and Self-Efficacy. It was recommended among others that the university institutionalize structured online counselling programs focusing on stress management, goal setting, and self-efficacy enhancement to promote students' psychological well-being and academic success.

Keywords: Counsellor, Online Counselling, Stress Management, Self-Efficacy, Stressors,

INTRODUCTION

Across the globe, increasing academic workload, competitive learning environments, and emerging psychosocial stressors have made psycho-academic adjustment a critical concern in higher education. Studies from different regions indicate that many university students experience difficulties adjusting psychologically and academically to the demands of tertiary education, often manifesting in heightened stress, reduced self-efficacy, and declining academic engagement (Auerbach, Mortier, Bruffaerts, Alonso, Benjet, Cuijpers & Kessler., 2018; Stallman, 2017).

Similar concerns have been documented within the Nigerian higher education system. Nigerian undergraduates including those at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi are increasingly confronted with academic pressure, financial constraints, limited access to counselling services, and socio-economic stressors, all of which may negatively affect their psycho-academic adjustment (Afolayan, Donald, Onasoga, Babafemi, & Agama, 2016; Adeoye, Adeyemi, & Aremu, 2020). These researches suggest that difficulties in managing stress and maintaining psychological stability among

Nigerian students are often associated with poor class attendance, low participation in academic activities, and examination-related anxiety, thereby raising concerns about students' overall academic success and adjustment. Consequently, understanding psycho-academic adjustment has become essential, as it captures how university students psychologically cope with academic demands while effectively engaging in core academic activities within their learning environments.

Online counselling has emerged as an effective tool for stress management, particularly among students navigating academic, social, and personal pressures. One key benefit is the accessibility it provides, enabling students to receive professional support without the barriers of distance or scheduling conflicts. Taylor and Stanton (2013), emphasize that the immediacy and convenience of online counselling allow students to access timely interventions, which can prevent stress from escalating into more severe psychological conditions. Through online counselling, students can explore coping strategies such as cognitive reframing, mindfulness, and time management, which are essential for reducing stress. Effective stress management involves identifying stressors, understanding their impact, and developing coping mechanisms to restore balance and well-being. Common techniques include relaxation exercises such as deep breathing, meditation, and progressive muscle relaxation; physical activities like walking, running, or yoga; time management skills that prioritize tasks and reduce procrastination; and seeking social support from friends, family, or counsellors.

In academic environments, students often benefit from structured stress management programs that incorporate mindfulness training, counselling services, and resilience-building workshops. Moreover, the growing use of technology in mental health care, including virtual counselling and mobile health apps, has made stress management tools more accessible and personalized. Online counselling helps in cultivating a positive mindset, practicing gratitude, setting realistic goals, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle with adequate sleep and nutrition are also essential components of managing stress effectively. Ultimately, stress management is not about eliminating stress entirely but about learning to respond to it constructively, thereby enhancing emotional resilience, academic performance, and overall quality of life. Online counselling provides clients with opportunities to learn how to respond constructively to stress.

Online counselling plays a pivotal role in enhancing self-efficacy among students by addressing barriers to confidence and providing tools for personal growth. One significant advantage of online counselling is its accessibility, which allows students to seek support without the constraints of physical locations or rigid schedules. Usher and Pajares (2019), highlighted that online counselling sessions focused on cognitive-behavioural techniques help students identify and challenge negative self-beliefs, fostering a stronger sense of self-efficacy. These interventions often include setting achievable goals, problem-solving, and providing constructive feedback, which empower students to take ownership of their growth and develop a belief in their ability to succeed.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the increasing prevalence of stress, low self-efficacy, and poor academic engagement among undergraduates has emerged as a significant concern to counsellors in higher education. The demands of adapting to a competitive academic environment, coupled with societal pressures, have left many students feeling overwhelmed and unable to cope effectively. Consequently, issues such as poor class attendance, minimal participation, reduced resilience, and struggles during examinations have become widespread, ultimately undermining students' academic success and overall well-being.

Traditional counselling services, although valuable, are often underutilized by students due to stigma, time constraints, and limited accessibility. This gap has led to a growing interest in online counselling as an innovative, accessible, and flexible alternative. Online counselling has the potential to provide timely psychological support, enhance stress management and improve self-efficacy, all of which are critical for navigating academic and personal challenges. It is against this backdrop that the current study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by investigating the impact of online counselling on stress management and self-efficacy, academic engagement among undergraduates in Fr. Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the impact of online counselling on stress-management and self-efficacy of undergraduate students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the impact of online counselling on stress-management of undergraduate students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.
2. investigate the impact of online counselling on self-efficacy of undergraduate students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the impact of online counselling on stress-management of undergraduate students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of online counselling on self-efficacy of undergraduate students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

1. Online counselling has no significant impact on online counselling on stress-management of undergraduate students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.
2. Online counselling has no significant impact on online counselling on self-efficacy of undergraduate students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was used for this study. This design is essentially cross-sectional and describes and interprets what exists at present. It gathers information from a relatively large number of people or items considered to be a representative sample of the population (Emaikwu, 2022). Its scope is vast as it is concerned with conditions or relationships that exist, practices that prevail, beliefs or points of view or attitudes that are held, processes that are on-going, influences that are being felt and trends that are developing in education (Ajai & Amuche, 2015). This design was preferred because it is concerned mainly with finding and describing what is in existence and obtainable. In the current study, the researcher aims to describe the impact of online counselling on stress-management and self-efficacy of undergraduate students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Population and Sample

The population of this study was 25,843 undergraduates from eight Faculties in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria (Office of the Registrar, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria, 2024) A multistage sampling procedure was employed in selecting the respondents. At the first stage, the stratified sampling technique was used to divide the population into eight strata based on faculties. These faculties and their respective undergraduate populations were Arts (4,048), Education (3,780), Environmental Sciences (448), Health Sciences (3,009), Law (957), Management Sciences (2,194), Sciences (4,615), and Social Sciences (6,792). This stratification was necessary to ensure adequate representation of students from all faculties in the university.

A questionnaire titled “Online Counselling and Psycho-academic Adjustment Scale (OCPAS)” was administered to gather data. The instrument was divided into six clusters, viz; clusters A, B, C, D, E and F. Cluster A elicited statements on impact of online counselling on management of stress, Cluster B elicited statements on impact of online counselling on self-efficacy, Cluster C elicited statements on impact of online counselling on resilience, Cluster D elicited items on impact of online counselling on class attendance, Cluster E elicited items on impact of online counselling on class participation and Cluster F elicited statements on impact of online counselling on writing examination. Each of the clusters had 5 statements making a total of 30 items. Respondents indicated their agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the options of Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1, Disagree (D) – 2, Agree (A) – 3 and Strongly Agree (SA) – 4.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the Impact of Online Counselling on Stress-Management of Undergraduate Students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean Scores of Impact of Online Counselling on Stress Management.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	σ	Decision
1	Online counselling has helped me identify the major sources of stress in my academic life.	100	210	48	36	2.95	.860	Agree
2	I feel more emotionally stable after participating in online counselling.	220	138	18	18	3.42	.782	Agree
3	Online counselling has provided me with effective strategies to manage stress.	165	187	32	10	3.29	.722	Agree
4	I can now balance academic responsibilities better due to online counselling.	112	225	39	18	3.09	.747	Agree
5	Online counselling sessions have reduced the level of stress I experience during academic assessments.	120	190	60	24	3.03	.837	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		$\bar{X}= 3.156$		SD = .0789		Agree		

Table 1 summarizes respondents' perceptions of the impact of online counselling on stress management. The mean scores for items 1 to 5 ranged from 2.95 to 3.42, with corresponding standard deviations between .722 and .860, all of which are above the 2.50 cut-off point, indicating agreement on each item. Respondents agreed that online counselling helped them identify sources of academic stress, enhanced emotional stability, provided effective stress-management strategies, improved balance of academic responsibilities, and reduced stress during assessments. The cluster mean of 3.156 with a cluster standard deviation of .0789 further confirms that online counselling has a positive impact on stress management among undergraduates of Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Research Question 2 *What is the Impact of Online Counselling on Self-Efficacy of Undergraduate Students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean Scores of Impact of Online Counselling on Self-Efficacy.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	σ	Decision
6	Online counselling has increased my confidence in handling academic challenges.	340	44	10	0	3.84	.433	Agree
7	I believe in my ability to succeed academically after engaging in online counselling.	170	185	29	10	3.31	.717	Agree
8	Online counselling has helped me set realistic academic goals towards achieving them.	130	150	66	48	2.92	.990	Agree
9	I am now more confident in participating in academic discussions due to online counselling.	120	250	20	4	3.23	.585	Agree
10	Online counselling has enhanced my belief in my capacity to excel in examinations.	145	185	42	24	3.14	.837	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		$\bar{X}= 3.288$		SD= .7124		Agree		

Table 2 presents respondents' views on the impact of online counselling on self-efficacy. The mean scores for items 6 to 10 ranged from 2.92 to 3.84, with standard deviations between .433 and .990, all

exceeding the 2.50 cut-off point, indicating agreement across all items. Respondents agreed that online counselling increased their confidence in handling academic challenges, strengthened their belief in academic success, supported realistic goal setting, improved confidence in academic discussions, and enhanced belief in their capacity to excel in examinations. The cluster mean of 3.288 with a cluster standard deviation of .7124 further indicates that online counselling has a positive impact on self-efficacy among undergraduates of Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (χ^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Online counselling has no significant the Impact on Stress-Management of Undergraduate Students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Table 7: Chi-Square Test of Impact of Online Counselling on Stress Management.

Response	Observed	Expected	df.	Level of sign.	χ^2 cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	248.985	.000	Sig.
Strongly Agree	120	98.5					
Agree	217	98.5					
Disagree	39	98.5					
Strongly Disagree	18	98.5					
Total	394						

Table 7 reveals Chi-square = 248.985, df =3 and p = 0.00. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that online counselling has no significant impact on stress management among undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This implies that online counselling had significant positive perceived impact on stress management among undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

Online counselling has no significant the Impact on Self-Efficacy on Undergraduate Students in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Table 8: Chi-Square Test of Impact of Online Counselling on Self-Efficacy.

Response	Observed	Expected	df.	Level of sign.	χ^2 cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	245.289	.000	Sig.
Strongly Agree	145	98.5					
Agree	201	98.5					
Disagree	38	98.5					
Strongly Disagree	10	98.5					
Total	394						

Table 8 reveals Chi-square = 245.289, df =3 and p = 0.00. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that online counselling has no significant impact of Self-Efficacy on undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This implies that online counselling had significant positive impact on Self-Efficacy on academic performance of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research was organized around the research questions and hypotheses.

The first hypothesis of the study revealed that online counselling has significant positive impact on stress management on undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria. This finding implies that undergraduate students who engage in online counselling perceive it as an effective

means of managing academic, emotional, and personal stress. It suggests that online counselling provides students with access to professional guidance and coping strategies that help them handle the pressures associated with academic life. This result aligns with the growing recognition that virtual or online counselling serves as an accessible, flexible, and effective alternative to traditional face-to-face counselling, particularly for young adults accustomed to digital interaction. Through virtual platforms, students can seek psychological support conveniently and confidentially, which encourages openness and timely intervention in managing stress-related challenges. The positive perception of online counselling on stress management may be attributed to its alignment with the realities of contemporary undergraduate life, where academic demands coexist with social, financial, and personal pressures. Online counselling appears to lower structural barriers such as time constraints, stigma, and limited availability of on-campus counsellors, thereby increasing students' willingness to seek help when stress symptoms emerge.

The second hypothesis of the study revealed that online counselling has significant positive impact on self-efficacy on undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria. This finding indicates that students perceive virtual counselling as a valuable means of building confidence in their academic abilities and personal problem-solving. This suggests that online counselling not only provides emotional support but also helps students develop a stronger sense of competence and control over academic tasks. The students with initially low self-efficacy benefited the most, emphasizing the transformative potential of online counselling. Providing structured guidance, personalized feedback, and opportunities for reflection, online counselling may help students internalize strategies for overcoming academic challenges, thereby strengthening their self-efficacy. The flexible and confidential nature of online platforms allows students to engage at their own pace, experiment with problem-solving approaches, and build confidence without the fear of judgment. This enhanced perception of competence can translate into greater initiative, persistence, and resilience in academic tasks, suggesting that integrating online counselling into university support services could foster both psychological and academic development, particularly for students who may otherwise be hesitant to seek traditional counselling.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that online counselling has significant impact on Stress Management and Self-Efficacy on undergraduate in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria. Specifically, online counselling positively influences students' study habits, motivation to learn, academic performance, class attendance, class participation, and examination writing skills. Through online counselling, students develop better time management, confidence, emotional stability, and engagement in academic activities. It also helps them overcome challenges such as anxiety, low motivation, and poor concentration, thereby enhancing their overall academic adjustment. These outcomes suggest that online counselling is not only an effective academic support mechanism but also a vital tool for promoting students' psychological well-being and educational success.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. It is recommended that the university counsellors should establish structured online counselling programmes that focus on stress management techniques such as mindfulness, relaxation exercises, and time management to help students cope with academic and personal pressures effectively.
2. Counsellors should design online sessions that emphasize goal setting, self-reflection, and positive reinforcement to strengthen students' belief in their abilities to succeed academically and personally.
3. Counsellors should utilize online counselling platforms to monitor and encourage consistent class attendance by addressing underlying motivational or psychological barriers that contribute to absenteeism.

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